

ROLE-PLAYING GAMES AS AN EDUCATOR OF STUDENTS' CONSCIOUSNESS, DISCIPLINE, AND COMPETENCE.

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Annotation. For students, role-play is a gaming activity in which they take on certain roles and perform them. Due to the game, learners quickly develop skills of dialogical speech, the ability to react quickly and to improvise. In addition to training, the role-playing game has great educational value. It helps to unite the student team, involving the active work of shy students. Role-playing games help to educate or develop consciousness, discipline, cooperation the ability to defend their point of view.

Key words. Role-playing game, self-management, game process, dialogical speech, participants, performance, education

The game along with work and study is one of the main activities of man, the amazing phenomenon of our existence. The game as a cultural phenomenon teaches, educates, develops, socializes, entertains, and gives rest. The author of the theory of the spiritual development of humans in the game first proposed the idea of using games in the general system of education, in the preparation of humans to work through the game. The researcher argued that simultaneous desire, sensation, and representation combined in the game. By definition Slavko “Game is an active in terms of situation, aimed at the reconstruction and assimilation of social experience, which develops and improves self-management behavior [2.].

Role-playing game is a game with an entertainment character, in which participants take specific roles and collectively create a story or follow an existing one. Participants make decisions based on the image of the character, and the

actions completed by the success or failure according to a certain system of rules, norms, and principles. Within the rules, players can improvise which helps to further develop and improve of language skills of students [4.].

Role-playing games in a foreign language must satisfy the following three basic requirements:

1) They should be adequate for learning dialogical speech at every stage of learning. Training dialogical speech distinguishes three main stages: a) adoption of dialogical unity b) mastering micro dialogue c) making their dialogues.

2) Role play must correspond to students' psycho-age characteristics and interests.

3) Role-playing games used in teaching foreign language dialogical speech, should also reflect the personal experience of students and promote broadening the context of their activities.

The following components form the structure of the role-playing games [3.]:

a) the roles assumed by participants in the game process

b) gaming activities that help participants implement the selected role

c) use of objects, in which real objects replace the game

d) teaching – speech situation

e) the real relations between people which manifest themselves in a variety of replicas, and observations that help to regulate the game development.

The content of each game is revealed due to the performance of selected roles by students. The play acts as a way of organizing. While creating a situation it is necessary to take into account the circumstances of reality and the relationship of the interactants. The following components of the situation are distinguished: subject; object; the relation of subject to object; and the conditions of speech act.

The use of role-play in language learning contributes to positive changes in the speech of students in qualitative (variety of dialogical unity, initiative speech partners, emotionality of words) and quantitative (correctness of speech, volume of speech, rate of speech) relationships.

Most authors consider it appropriate to conduct a game (to play) at the final stage of work on the subject because not all students can freely improvise in a role-play without preparation. “In the process of role-playing games, there is simultaneous improvement and development of skills in the use of the language of material, but it is at this stage the peripheral task, the main thing is communication, motivated by the situation and role. Therefore the role play should take place at the final stage of work on the topic”[5.]. However some authors claim that role-playing games should be introduced in the educational process at an early stage of work on the topic that the students are used to this sort of work gradually, as otherwise, it’s impossible to achieve the desired results from games because of the barrier, which occurs when an unusual form of communication, typical for a role-playing game. One more important thing in role-playing games is selecting a topic, that carries a problematic issue, stimulates the exchange of views, and prompts reflection. Elementary tasks are not interesting for students and constant control of teachers also limits their initiative [1:38]. It should be noted that the teacher has to make significant efforts to maintain motivation and interest among students. Using role-play, the teacher can develop all kinds of speech activities for students primarily oral speech which is the leading form of speech activity at the further levels of education. Role play helps to ensure (promote) that students’ speech becomes more substantial, and more complicated in the structure of language and speech material. Teachers must understand that properly organized role play in the classroom – is not an empty exercise, it not only delivers maximum pleasure to the student, but it is a powerful tool for development, using forming a full-fledged personality.

Summing up, it should be noted that role play is inherent in the methodology of teaching a foreign language to develop skills in oral speech and also increase student’s motivation for the subject.

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